

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Heparin and β 2-microglobulin amyloidogenesis

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Abstract

β 2-Microglobulin (β 2M) occurs as a precursor protein in dialysis-related amyloidosis (DRA), which is a major complication in lives of patients undergoing dialysis. However, the underlying mechanism by which a native β 2M transform into an amyloid β 2M remain unclear. This disease has developed exclusively in interstitial tissues, which suggest possible implication of extracellular matrix substances in amyloidogenesis of this precursor protein. By using our monoclonal antibody specific for amyloid β 2M, we investigated the function of heparin, that is, one of the glycosaminoglycans, as associated with amyloidogenic conversion of the β 2M molecule. We confirmed that heparin induced a dose-dependent and time-dependent unfolding at the C-terminal region of the β 2M molecule, which led to amyloidogenic transformation of the β 2M molecule and brought about intermolecular interactions between β 2M and substances in the interstitial matrix such as GAGs and collagen.

Keywords: β 2-microglobulin; Dialysis-related amyloidosis; Heparin; Glycosaminoglycans

1. Introduction

Dialysis-related amyloidosis (DRA) is one of the major complications that is inevitably associated with long-term dialysis treatment used in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). Every type of amyloidosis has a specific precursor protein as a causative factor. In 1984, Gejyo et al. identified β 2-microglobulin (β 2M) as a precursor protein of DRA [1]. This small protein, i.e., with a molecular size of 11,800 Da, exists on membranes of all nucleated cells and is mostly degraded, not excreted, by the kidneys. Amounts produced were estimated to be about 150-220 mg/day/ 60-70 kg body weight, in healthy people [2]; serum β 2M levels increase and are found to be extremely high at the end stage of CKD. β 2M moves freely through vascular walls and disseminates throughout the extracellular space, where large amounts of glycosaminoglycans (GAGs) and collagen exist. At the end stage of CKD, β 2M concentrations in interstitial tissues also increase, supposedly enough to strengthen interactions between β 2M and substances in the interstitial matrix such as GAGs and collagen. The general belief is that nonphysiological interplay among these substances contributes to the clinical characteristics of this type of amyloidosis such that it initiates exclusively with arthropathy of the osteoarticular structures [3, 4].

In this review, we first explain the amyloidogenic propensity of β 2M molecules, after which we discuss the reason why we focused on heparin, and finally we describe the results of our current work, with implications for the role of heparin in β 2M amyloidogenesis.

2. Heparin and Heparan Sulfate

Heparin has been well known as an anticoagulant agent and is routinely used throughout Japan in clinical practices such as hemodialysis, for more than 60 years. Heparin is one of GAGs and highly sulfated form of heparan sulfate (HS), which

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contribute its high negative charge density. On the other hand, heparan sulfate proteoglycan (HSPG) consists of a core protein and another type of GAGs. HSPG is distributed systematically throughout the whole body as a major component of connective tissues, as is collagen. In addition, the number of SO_3 groups per sugar unit of heparan sulfate is close to that of heparin.

In 1987, the first report appeared of the coexistence of HSPG in tissue samples containing amyloid that had been obtained from specimens with experimental systemic amyloidosis that was due to serum amyloid A complicated by chronic inflammation [5, 6]. Subsequent reports were published of the coexistence of HSPG with amyloid β in Alzheimer's disease [7] and with amyloidosis including DRA [8]. This histological evidence led to Snow's concept that GAGs in interstitial tissues dose-dependently promote and stabilize amyloid fibril formation (fibrillogenesis) [9]. With regard to β 2M, a binding activity of β 2M with heparin was also reported [10]. That such GAG action on fibrillogenesis depends on the number of SO_3 groups has increasingly become clear, but the underlying mechanism by which β 2M interacts with GAGs remains uncertain [11]. Among these studies with β 2M and GAGs, the report of Yamamoto et al. about treatment of β 2M with trifluoroethanol seemed to be intriguing because trifluoroethanol induces unfolding of the β 2M molecule as well as guanidine hydrochloride and sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) [12]. We believe that unfolding of the β 2M molecule, especially unfolding in the C-terminal region, must be a prerequisite for both intermolecular interactions and formation of an amyloid nucleus [13]. Thus, in our study we focused on the actions of heparin in the unfolding of the β 2M molecule.

3. β 2M and Its Intermediate Conformer

β 2M consists of the N- and C-terminal portions and the core. Seven anti-parallel β -strands constitute two β -sheets in the rigid core and acquire a globular configuration by means of approximately 30 inter-strand hydrogen bonds and an S-S bond between Cys25 and Cys80 (B and F strands) at the center. Seven β -strands have been named conventionally as A, B, C, D, E, F, and G, from the N-term to the C-term (Figure 1). The core consists of two β -sheets, i.e., one comprising strands A, B, D, and E, and another comprising strands C, F, and G. Five N-terminal amino acids are temporarily detached from the core surface, even in the native molecule in body fluids. Thus, a native β 2M molecule coexists ubiquitously in dynamic equilibrium with a partially unfolded intermediate molecule (conformer), even in the physiological state, because of temporal breaking of hydrogen bond in strand A [14]. The C-terminal portion seem to be folded toward the inside in the global configuration because of the retained hydrogen bond between Asp96 and Met99. In an experimental study, several intermediate conformers with definite, albeit partial, unfolded species were confirmed as occurring in a transitional process from native molecule to amyloid molecule [15]. The unfolding of the β -sheet structure induced by breaking the interstrand hydrogen bonds give rise to changes in the surface charge of the molecule. Thus, we can confirm the unfolding as an alteration of the profile in capillary electrophoresis (CE) [16].

Figure 1 Seven strands in native β 2-microglobulin (β 2M) (Protein Data Bank code 2D4F)

We had first used CE to determine the presence of the intermediate β 2M conformer in serum from patients undergoing hemodialysis, and we confirmed that the intermediate β 2M conformer exists, ubiquitously, in a state of dynamic equilibrium of approximately 1:10, with a native conformer in serum obtained not only from patients undergoing hemodialysis but also from healthy persons [14]. However, a more deformed (destructured) profile was recognized in serum after the hemodialysis procedure in which interstitial fluid was returned (backflow) into circulation from the interstitial space by a rebound phenomenon associated with the hemodialysis procedure itself [17]. A more deformed profile on CE indicates a molecular population of more unfolded conformers, which migrated at a delayed retention time on CE. In contrast, the β 2M profile before hemodialysis was constantly like that in a healthy person, which suggested two possibilities: spontaneous refolding into a native conformer in circulation (intravascular space) during dialysis-off days or sequestration in the extravascular space where both GAGs and collagen are abundant. A kinetic study with ^{125}I -labeled β 2M by Vincent et al. indicated the latter possibility [18]. They had reported a considerable amount of unrecovered ^{125}I -labeled β 2M, which was not exchangeable with β 2M in the vascular pool, i.e., no return pool called a capitation compartment existed. We believe that this non-exchangeable compartment must be responsible for the large accumulation of β 2M that is retained yearly in the extravascular space during dialysis, even if serum β 2M concentrations leveled off. van Ypersele de Strihou et al. estimated an accumulation of β 2M in the extravascular space of about 500 g or more during 10 years of hemodialysis [19]. Even with current on-line hemodiafiltration, Canaud et al. estimated a β 2M accumulation of 700 mg/body weight/week, which would reach submillimolar or millimolar levels in the extravascular space in several years, which may be comparable with experimental levels [20]. These supraphysiological concentrations are supposedly important for development of DRA, because involvement of the osteoarticular system is lacking in D76N β 2M amyloidosis by virtue of no association with renal impairment [21].

One of our original purposes in this study with amyloidogenic β 2M was to identify this capitation compartment, as suggested by the kinetic study in patients with dialysis, which we mentioned above. Another purpose concerned finding diagnostic clues about β 2M intermediate conformers. Regarding intermediate conformers, two experimental types were proposed as follows: a reversible conformer that can refold into the native conformer and an irreversible conformer, which is an amyloidogenic conformer and cannot refold. McParland et al. reported that the unfolding in the C-terminus may be a critical feature leading to reversibility of the intermediates [22]. However, on CE, we did not directly detect the irreversible conformer in a patient's serum. Moreover, even with the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay with the monoclonal antibody specific for the C-terminus from Ile92 to Met99, i.e., mAb92-99, we did not detect the amyloidogenic conformer in serum [23]. Therefore, we speculate that the amyloidogenic conformer may be formed exclusively in the extravascular space by interaction with GAGs and may remain there. We believe that once the unfolding process proceeds to form the amyloidogenic conformer, the conformer is immobilized in situ and does not pass through the vascular wall and return to the circulation, except for the limited situation involving the rebound phenomenon at the terminal phase of hemodialysis [17].

Consequently, our data indicated that amyloidogenic intermediates of β 2M are not present in circulation, which was confirmed by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry [24].

4. $\Delta\text{N6}\beta$ 2M

$\Delta\text{N6}\beta$ 2M is an amyloidogenic variant of β 2M, not an intermediate variant, that lacks the 6 N-terminal amino acids that have been found in amyloid tissue from patients undergoing dialysis [25]. Although several artificial fragments of β 2M such as the E strand and ΔK56 - β 2M had proved to be amyloidogenic in experimental studies [26, 27], the $\Delta\text{N6}\beta$ 2M variant is the natural variant found in amyloid tissues from patients with DRA and is assumed to be a degradation product produced by trypsin from native or aggregated β 2M that has accumulated in the interstitial space [28]. Bellotti et al. reported the reversibility (refolding) to the soluble conformer of this variant in an ex vivo study, but a highly fibrillogenic variant had been confirmed experimentally by several researchers including us [29-32]. Although spontaneous fibril formation by this variant was not demonstrated at concentrations of 0.2 mM in the report of Borysik et al. (pH 7.4), our recent study indicated definite fibril formation at 0.1 mM (1 mg/mL) (pH 7.4), a concentration that is supposedly comparable with concentrations in the interstitial space of patients undergoing long-term hemodialysis (Figure 2) [32-34]. Although the C-terminal side strands in $\Delta\text{N6}\beta$ 2M—E, F, and G strands—have reportedly been mostly conserved, according to nuclear magnetic resonance analysis, our study using mAb92-99 demonstrated the unfolding of the C-terminus of this variant [23]. Thus, 4 hydrogen bonds between the F and G strands may be partially broken. In addition, the isoelectric point of $\Delta\text{N6}\beta$ 2M should be lower than the 6.4 value of native β 2M because of the loss of arginine and lysine in the N-terminus, but the $\Delta\text{N6}\beta$ 2M peak was found at a delayed retention time by CE analysis, 2 min later than native β 2M, and the $\Delta\text{N6}\beta$ 2M peak on CE differed from that of intermediate β 2M found in serum (Figure 3) [23]. As far as we know, this variant has as yet never been reported in serum. The assumption has been that $\Delta\text{N6}\beta$ 2M is limited to the extravascular space by protease (trypsin) and cannot return to the circulation.

Figure 2 Fibrillogenesis of $\Delta N6\beta 2M$ shown by electron microscopy according to the method of Domanska et al [34]. The $\Delta N6\beta 2M$ fibrils were prepared by incubating 0.1 mM of the purified protein at 37 °C in 50 mM phosphate buffer and 100 mM NaCl, pH 7.4, in the presence of 20% TFE and 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ fibrillar seeds. Fibrils were collected after 1 month by centrifugation

Figure 3 Capillary electrophoresis profiles. (A) Native $\beta 2M$: a single peak with a sloping shoulder at the retention time of 12 min. (B) $\Delta N6\beta 2M$: a double peak at the retention time of 14 min. (C) Mixture of native $\beta 2M$ and $\Delta N6\beta 2M$. Figure adapted from ref. [23]

As mentioned above, the concentrations of $\beta 2M$ that accumulate in the extravascular space must reach levels as high as submillimolar concentrations in patients receiving maintenance hemodialysis for more than 10 years, which may be sufficient concentrations for amyloidogenic molecules to cause intermolecular interactions and to form aggregations and/or oligomers or to generate $\Delta N6\beta 2M$ via protease [35].

5. C-Terminal Unfolding in $\beta 2M$ Induced by Heparin

In the clinical setting of hemodialysis, two types of heparins, i.e., high-molecular-weight heparin (HMH) and low-molecular-weight heparin (LMH), have been used routinely. Although clinical application of LMH has been now approved, HMH is still generally used in hemodialysis [36]. We previously reported the interactions of native $\beta 2M$ and two amyloidogenic $\beta 2M$ variants, i.e., $\Delta N6\beta 2M$ and D76N $\beta 2M$, with HMH and LMH [37]. Our binding study not only confirmed the binding of $\Delta N6\beta 2M$ and D76N $\beta 2M$ with HMH but also suggested the binding potential of native $\beta 2M$ with HMH (Figure 4A). The K_D (dissociation constant) values of native $\beta 2M$, $\Delta N6\beta 2M$, and D76N $\beta 2M$ as related to HMH were 3.71×10^{-6} M, 2.07×10^{-8} M, and 1.72×10^{-7} M, respectively. The K_D value of $\Delta N6\beta 2M$ was low enough to be comparable to the K_D value of $\Delta N6\beta 2M$ with the specific monoclonal antibody mAb92-99. In contrast, LMH showed no association even with $\Delta N6\beta 2M$ (Figure 4B). Because GAGs in the interstitial space are rich in heparin molecules, $\beta 2M$ has been

trapped and accumulated time-dependently in the interstitial space in patients undergoing hemodialysis, and β 2M levels are expected to reach values as high as millimolar concentrations in 10 years or more. It is interesting that HMH induced a C-terminal unfolding of native β 2M, which indicated production of an amyloidogenic intermediate, i.e., β 2M92-99, in a time-dependent manner (Figure 4C). LMH, however, did not cause C-terminal unfolding in native β 2M, even after incubation for 24 h [37].

Figure 4 Analysis of the interactions of β 2M variants with high-molecular-weight heparin (HMH) (A) and low-molecular-weight heparin (LMH) (B), and heparin-dependent interaction of native β 2M with mAb92-99 (C) via a biolayer interferometry technique. β 2M variants— Δ N6 β 2M (solid line, —), D76N β 2M (dashed line, ---), and native β 2M (dotted line, ...)—were injected onto the HMH-immobilized (A) or LMH-immobilized (B) sensor chip, respectively. Native β 2M incubated with HMH for 0 h or 24 h was injected onto the mAb92-99-immobilized sensor chip (C). Figure adapted from ref. [37]

Furthermore, our study showed a distinct difference in the strength of the bond between HMH and the two β 2M variants Δ N6 β 2M and D76N β 2M. Valleix et al. first reported the amyloidogenicity of D76N β 2M, which is a natural amyloidogenic mutant [21]. However, patients with D76N β 2M showed no signs of CKD, and their serum β 2M levels continued to be close to normal, that is, approximately 0.1 μ M. Δ N6 β 2M had a moderate response with HMH even at 0.1 μ M, compared with the response of D76N β 2M, at 1.0 μ M, which showed a 10-fold difference in the intensity of the binding response for these two variants. A similar difference in collagen-binding affinity was reported for Δ N6 β 2M and native β 2M [28]. Because the C-terminus of D76N β 2M was confirmed as unfolded, as was that of Δ N6 β 2M, a difference in binding response levels for the two amyloidogenic variants may result from a difference in the populations of molecules with C-terminal unfolding, i.e., molecules with C-terminal unfolding should occur considerably more commonly in Δ N6 β 2M than in D76N β 2M [21, 37].

During amyloidogenesis, an intermediate molecule of a precursor protein with a partially unfolded structure had been generally known to be a key molecule. For β 2M, we had verified that the unfolding at the C-terminus from Ile92 to Met99 was the key process for amyloidogenicity of this precursor protein [23]. Our study demonstrated that HMH could cause a C-terminal β 2M concentration to change to 1 μ M, which is comparable to the serum concentration in patients undergoing hemodialysis.

A majority of SO_3^- groups in GAGs, as in SDSs, has been known to induce conformational changes in proteins. For β 2M, several studies indicated amyloidogenic conversion depending on the large number of SO_3^- groups in GAGs [28]. As is well known, heparin is highly negatively charged and highly sulfated (SO_3^- groups). Although we have not studied dose-dependent effects of heparin on the C-terminal unfolding of β 2M, we believe that the number of SO_3^- groups in heparin may make the difference in the results for HMH and LMH. The conformation of the β 2M molecule is maintained by multiple intramolecular hydrogen bonds, which may be broken, partly by the SO_3^- groups.

Our studies together pointed to two actions of HMH with β 2M, i.e., direct binding and induction of C-terminal unfolding. The former may result in an accumulation of β 2M in the interstitial space and the latter may induce amyloidogenicity of β 2M. LMH, however, showed no definite interaction, even with Δ N6 β 2M, which indicated a superior clinical availability compared with HMH as an anticoagulant in long-term hemodialysis, in which DRA is a serious complication.

6. Discussion

According to a concept that was based on several experiments, amyloid fibrils form via two serial processes: first, formation of an amyloid nucleus (nucleation) and then subsequent fibril formation [38]. Thus far, since the study of interstitial substances by Snow and Kisilevsky, both GAGs and collagen have proved to induce and stabilize fibrillogenesis [5, 6], and a scaffolding effect of collagen via electrostatic action was confirmed as a factor contributing to fibrillogenesis of β 2M [39]. For GAGs, an association between sulfated GAGs and β 2M fibrillogenesis was also proved but a relationship with the nucleation process was not yet fully clarified [12, 33]. The nucleation process is a rate-limiting step in amyloid formation, which suggests that nucleation is unlikely to proceed spontaneously *in vivo* because of the high energy barrier [38]. However, C-terminal unfolding is believed to lower the energy barrier and quickly facilitate the nucleation process. Nucleation is thought to start by means of formation of highly unfolded intermediate molecules, and such unfolded intermediate molecules are poorly reversible to native molecules or are irreversible [31]. In clinical settings, these kinds of intermediate β 2M molecules may be generated and limited to the extravascular space, where reversible intermediates transferred from the vascular space undergo more unfolding by means of interactions with sulfated GAGs. Such intermediates supposedly have extensively unfolded C-termini that differ from the intermediate conformers that occur in serum and are likely to induce intermolecular interactions. Intermolecular interactions involve the generation of aggregates or the formation of oligomers, which leads to nucleation. In addition, β 2M trapped by the GAG network is also believed likely to undergo cleavage or truncation via proteases such as trypsin and to generate Δ N6 β 2M, i.e., the amyloidogenic variant. In the body, protease activation is essentially regulated by protease inhibitors such as α ₂-macroglobin. Thus, as previously reported, circulating levels of the α ₂-macroglobin- β 2M complex were expected as an indicator of Δ N6 β 2M generated in the extravascular space in patients undergoing hemodialysis [13]. As shown here, Δ N6 β 2M showed definite unfolding in the C-terminus. Such a variant with extensive unfolding can contribute directly to formation of the amyloid nucleus (nucleation) on its own. McParland et al. had revealed that the unfolding process proceeds in a specific order, not in a random order, such as beginning with the N-terminus and A strand, and then proceeding to the C-terminus and G strand [22]. The amyloidogenicity of intermediates is thought to depend on the reversibility of their refolding. To our knowledge, no report has as yet clarified the critical point of reversibility. However, as McParland pointed out, we also believe that the highly unfolded state such that both the C-terminus and G strand are unfolded may be necessary for amyloidogenic conversion of β 2M, which suggests partial breaking of 4 hydrogen bonds between the G- and F-strands, at least. Such an unfolded state can be detected by mAb92-99 [13, 23].

Eichner et al., however, had demonstrated that trans-isomerization of Pro32 is a critical event for β 2M amyloidogenicity [40], and Rennella et al. showed that Pro32 was trans-isomerized in I₂ (kinetic intermediate), as well as in the amyloid variant D76N β 2M [41]. However, which of these processes, i.e., Pro32 trans-isomerization or C-terminal unfolding, is responsible for the amyloidogenicity of Δ N6 β 2M and/or D76N β 2M remains unclear.

In our previous histological study with mAb92-99, which is the specific antibody for the C-terminus, we detected this kind of β 2M with extensive unfolding in pre-amyloid tissue where Congo red reactions remained negative [13]. A negative Congo red stain indicated the presence of immature fibril structures, i.e., protofibrils, which also suggested premature β 2M intermediates with extensive C-terminal unfolding. However, Chiti et al. had reported that their intermediate β 2M molecule, termed I₂, showed a definite binding both with Congo red and thioflavin T [42]. However, intermediate I₂ was experimentally identified as in transition from completely unfolded β 2M by guanidine hydrochloride, which may be more destructured than intermediate β 2M found in clinical settings.

Pro32 in I₂ had reportedly been trans-isomerized, but whether Pro32 or the unfolded C-terminus take an initiative role in amyloidogenesis remained to be determined; nevertheless, we believe that extensive unfolding (destructured) in the C-terminal region may be a prerequisite for intermolecular interactions and subsequent nucleation.

Three kinds of force including hydrogen bonds (H–H), hydrophobic interactions (CH₂–CH₂), and electrostatic interactions (NH₄⁺–O⁻) supposedly exist among the 7 strands in the β 2M molecule, and heparin can have an effect on all of them [43].

Therefore, C-terminal unfolding should be interpreted as being a net effect by heparin. As mentioned earlier, C-terminal unfolding is thought to enable intermolecular interactions, which may be also affected by heparin. We believe that heparin is implicated in multiple aspects of the nucleation process. A recent *in silico* study also suggested the importance of the unfolding in the C-terminus for β 2M amyloidogenicity (Figure 5) [44].

Figure 5 The I₂ intermediate populated by D76N β 2M, which features a well-preserved core and two unstructured and decoupled termini. The N- and C-termini are blue and red, respectively. The BC- and DE-loops are yellow and green, respectively. Figure adapted from Figure 1C in ref. [44]

Relini et al. had reported that heparin enhanced β 2M fibrillogenesis by collagen, which is of great importance from the clinical viewpoint because sulfated GAGs including heparin coexist ubiquitously with collagen in the body [28]. As demonstrated here, heparin gives rise to C-terminal unfolding to react with mAb92-99 in the β 2M molecule, which is sufficient to form the nucleus itself. Therefore, in vivo, heparin is expected to have a synergistic effect on nucleation as well as fibrillogenesis.

7. Conclusion

The unfolding in the C-terminal region from Ile92 to Met99 is a primary prerequisite for induction of the amyloidogenicity of β 2M. An essential and sufficient condition for this unfolding is regional accumulation of β 2M to concentrations as high as submillimolar values that are comparable to laboratory concentrations. By using HMH and LMH, we determined that sulfonated GAGs are critical both for formation of an amyloid nucleus and for this regional accumulation. This idea forms the foundation of our proposed “ β 2M shuttle hypothesis” in DRA [17]. Given that the nucleation process is a rate-limiting step in amyloid formation, the clinical importance of sulfated GAGs in interstitial tissue should be stressed. Therefore, the interstitial space may be the origin of amyloid β 2M. With reference to the amyloidogenicity of β 2M, we also described several features of Δ N6 β 2M, i.e., an amyloidogenic derivative.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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